

**ELEKTR XOTIRAGA EGA BO'LGAN INTEGRO-DIFFERENSIAL MAKSVELL TENGLAMASI
UCHUN TO'G'RI MASALA**

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ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu ishda elektr xotiraga ega bo'lgan integro-differensial Maksvell tenglamasi uchun to'g'ri masala qaraldi. Bunda Maksvell tenglamalar sistemasi ma'lum bir shartlar asosida bir o'lchamli integro-differensial Maksvell tenglamalar sistemasiga keltirildi. Yangi o'zgaruvchi kiritib, ba'zi almashtirishlardan so'ng kanonik ko'rinishdagi integro-differensial tenglama olindi. Kanonik ko'rinishdagi tenglama uchun Koshi masalasi qo'yildi. Masalaning yechimi mavjudligi va yagonaligi uchun asosiy teorema keltirildi. Masala yechimining mavjudligi ketma-ket yaqinlashish (Pikar) usuli yordamida ko'rsatildi, Gronuolla — Bellman tengsizligiga asosan yagonaligi isbotlandi.

ABSTRACT: In this paper, we consider a well-posed problem for Maxwell's integro-differential equation with electric memory. The system of Maxwell's equations was reduced to a one-dimensional integro-differential Maxwell's equation. After the introduction of a new variable and some changes, a canonical integro-differential equation is obtained. The Cauchy problem is placed before the canonical equation. The main existence and uniqueness theorem for the solution of the problem is given. The existence of a solution to the problem was demonstrated by the method of successive approximation, which turned out to be the only one based on the Gronwall-Bellman inequality.

Kalit so'zlar: Maksvell tenglamalar sistemasi, integro-differensial tenglamalar, Koshi masala, ketma-ket yaqinlashish usuli, Gronuolla — Bellman tengsizligi.

Keywords: Maxwell's system of equations, integro-differential equations, Cauchy problem, method of successive approximations, Gronwall-Bellman inequality.

KIRISH. Uch o'lchamli Maksvell tenglamalar sistemasini qaraylik. [1]

$$\nabla \times H = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} D(x, t) + \sigma E + J, \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \times E = -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} B(x, t), \quad B = 0, \quad D = \rho.$$

bunda $D = (D_1, D_2, D_3)$ va $B = (B_1, B_2, B_3)$ lar mos ravishda elektr va magnit maydon induksiylari bo'lib, quyidagi formulalar bilan bog'langan:

$$D(x, t) = \varepsilon E + \int_0^t \varphi(t - \tau) E(x, \tau) d\tau, \quad (2)$$

$$B(x, t) = \mu H + \int_0^t \psi(t - \tau) H(x, \tau) d\tau,$$

$E = (E_1, E_2, E_3)$ va $H = (H_1, H_2, H_3)$ lar esa mos ravishda elektr va magnit maydon kuchlanishi, $\varphi(t) = \text{diag}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3)$, $\psi(t) = \text{diag}(\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3)$ – diagonal matrisalar bo'lib xotira funksiyasini ifodalaydi, ε va μ elektr va magnit maydon sindiruvchanligi, $J = J(x, t) = (0, J_2(x, t), 0)$ – vektor funksiya tashqi elektr toki zichligini ifodalaydi, ε – muhit o'tkazuvchanligi. (1) ning uchinchi tenglamasi (1) ning ikkinchi tenglamasi va

$$(\mu H)|_{t=0} = 0. \quad (3)$$

shartdan kelib chiqadi.

(1) Maksvell tenglamalar sistemasida qatnashuvchi barcha ε , μ , σ parametrlar va J tashqi elektr toki zichligi x_1, x_2 koordinatalarga bog'lik bo'lmasin. faqat x_3 ga bog'liq bo'lsin. U holda (1) Maksvell tenglamalar sistemasi ham x_1, x_2 koordinatalarga bog'lik bo'lmagan sistemaga keladi va $E_1 = E_3 = H_2 = H_3 = 0$.

Masalan, ε , μ lar R sohada o'zgarmas $\varepsilon = 1$, $\mu = \text{const}$ va $\sigma = \sigma(x_3)$ bo'lsin. Shuningdek Maksvell tenglamalar sistemasi magnit xotiraga ega emas deb faraz qilamiz. Demak, bulardan kelib chiqqan holda (1), (2) Maksvell tenglamalar sistemasini quyidagi ko'rinishda yozamiz.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial E_2}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial H_1}{\partial x_3} + \int_0^t \varphi_2(\tau) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} E_2(x_3, t - \tau) d\tau + J_2(x_3, t) = 0, \\ \mu \frac{\partial H_1}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial E_2}{\partial x_3} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Dastlabki vaqt momentida muhit tinch holatda bo'lgan deb hisoblaymiz, ya'ni

$$E_2|_{t<0} = 0, \quad H_1|_{t<0} = 0 \quad (5)$$

(4) tenglamalar sistemasini yechish davomida biz, E_2 ga nisbatan ikkinchi tartibli xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial x_3^2} + \sigma \frac{\partial E_2}{\partial t} + \int_0^t \varphi_2(\tau) \frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial \tau^2}(x_3, t - \tau) d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} J_2(x_3, t) = 0. \quad (6)$$

Qulaylik uchun keying ishlarda $\varphi_2(t)$ funksiyani $\varphi(t)$ deb olamiz. Oxirida (4) tenglamalar sistemasining ikkinchi tenglamasini t o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha integrallab, (5) shartdan foydalansak H_1 ni E_2 ga bog'liq holda topish mumkin.

Ushbu

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial t^2}(x_3, t - \tau) = \frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial \tau^2}(x_3, t - \tau)$$

tenglikni hisobga olgan holda, (2.1.6) tenglamani

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial x_3^2} + \sigma \frac{\partial E_2}{\partial t} + \int_0^t \varphi(\tau) \frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial \tau^2}(x_3, t - \tau) d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} J_2(x_3, t) = 0. \quad (8)$$

ko'rinishga yozamiz. (8) integro-differensial tenglamaning integral hadini ikki marta bo'laklab integrallab quyidagi tenglamaga kelamiz:

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial^2 E_2}{\partial x_3^2} + (\sigma + \varphi(0)) \frac{\partial E_2}{\partial t} + \varphi'(t) E_2(x_3, t) + \int_0^t \varphi''(\tau) E_2(x_3, t - \tau) d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} J_2(x_3, t) = 0. \quad (9)$$

Yangi $u(x, t)$ funksiya kiritamiz:

$$E_2(y, t) = \exp\left\{-\frac{\sigma + \varphi(0)}{2} t\right\} u(y, t), \quad y \equiv x_3.$$

(8) tenglamani ushbu $u(x, t)$ funksiyaga nisbatan yozamiz va tenglamadagi integralni ikki marta bo'laklab integrallab quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} - \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + H(y)u(y, t) = \int_0^t k(\tau)u(y, t - \tau)d\tau + F(y, t) \quad (10)$$

bunda $H(y) = \varphi'(t)_{t=0} - \frac{(\sigma(y)+\varphi(0))^2}{4}$, $k(t) = \exp\left\{-\frac{\sigma+\varphi(0)}{2}t\right\} \varphi''(t)$ va $F(y, t) = \exp\left\{\frac{\sigma+\varphi(0)}{2}t\right\} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} J_2(y, t)$.

Quyidagicha yangi o'zgaruvchi kiritamiz:

$$z = z(y) = \sqrt{\mu}y.$$

U holda (10) integro - differensial tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishni oladi

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} + q(z)v(z, t) = \int_0^t k(\tau)v(z, t - \tau)d\tau + F_1(z, t) \quad (11)$$

bunda $q(z) = H\left(\frac{z}{\sqrt{\mu}}\right)$, $F_1(z, t) = F\left(\frac{z}{\sqrt{\mu}}, t\right)$, $v(z, t) = u\left(\frac{z}{\sqrt{\mu}}, t\right)$.

Shunday qilib, biz integro - differensial Maksvell tenglamalar sistemasidan (11) ko'rinishdagi bir o'chamli ikkinchi tartibli integro - differensial tenglamani hosil qildik. Endi (11) integro - differensial Maksvell tenglamasi uchun Koshi shartlarini qo'yib, (11) tenglamada qatnashgan $q(z)$, $k(t)$, va $F_1(z, t)$ funksiyalarni berilgan deb faraz qilib, $v(z, t)$ nomalum funksiyani topish bilan shug'ullanamiz.

MASALANING QO'YILISHI.

To'g'ri masala. $D := \{(z, t) | z \in R, t > 0\}$ sohada (10) integro - differensial tenglama uchun quyidagi Koshi masalasini qaraylik:

$$v(z, t)|_{t=0} = \eta(z), \quad (12)$$

$$v_t(z, t)|_{t=0} = \nu(z), \quad (13)$$

Tarif 1. D sohada (10) tenglamada qatnashgan $q(z)$, $k(t)$, va $F_1(z, t)$ funksiyalarni berilgan funksiyalar deb, (11) tenglamaning (12) va (13) shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $v(z, t)$ funksiyani topish masalasi tog'ri masala deyiladi.

Korrekt qo'yilgan masalalar nazariyasiga ko'ra, agar $q(z)$, $\eta(z)$, $\nu(z) \in C(R)$, $k(t) \in C(R_+)$, va $F_1(z, t) \in C(D)$ bo'lsa, (11) - (13) Koshi masalasi korrekt qo'yilgan bo'ladi. Bu holda (11) - (13) masalaning yechimiga umumlashgan yechim deyiladi

Tarif 2. Agar $q(z) \in C(R)$, $\eta(z) \in C^2(R)$, $v(z) \in C^1(R)$, $k(t) \in C(R_+)$, va $F_1(z, t)$, $F_{1_t}(z, t) \in C(D_T)$ bo'lsa, (11) -(13) Koshi masalasining klassik yechimi mavjud deyiladi va bu yechim $v(z, t) \in C^2(D_T)$ sinfga tegishli deyiladi, bunda $D_T := \{(z, t) | z \in R, 0 < t \leq T\}$ ko'rinishdagi yo'lakdan iborat.

Teskari masala. (11)- (13) masala yechimi va

$$v(z, t)|_{z=0} = f(t), \quad (14)$$

$$v_z(z, t)|_{z=0} = g(t), \quad (15)$$

shartlar yordamida $q(z) \in C(R)$ funksiyani topish maslasiga teskari masala deyiladi.

Boshqacha aytganda $\eta(z)$, $v(z)$, $k(t)$, $f(t)$, $g(t)$, $F_1(z, t)$ funksiyalarni berilgan funksiyalar deb, (11)-(15) masaladan $v(z, t)$ va $q(z)$ funksiyalarni topish masalasi teskari masala deyiladi.

D yarim tekislikda (z_0, t_0) nuqta olamiz. (11) tenglamaning (z_0, t_0) nuqtadan o'tuvchi xarakteristikalari va OZ o'q yordamida chegaralangan sohani

$$D(z_0, t_0) := \{z_0 - t_0 \leq z \leq z_0 + t_0, |z - z_0| \leq t - t_0\}$$

orqali belgilaymiz.

To'g'ri masala yechimining mavjudligi va yagonaligi haqidagi asosiy natija quyidagi teoremda keltirilgan.

NATIJALAR

Teorema. Agar har qanday $t_0 > 0$, $z_0 \in R$ sonlar uchun $q(z) \in C[z_0 - t_0, z_0 + t_0]$, $\eta(z) \in C^2[z_0 - t_0, z_0 + t_0]$, $v(z) \in C^1[z_0 - t_0, z_0 + t_0]$, $k(t) \in C[0, t_0]$, va $F_1(z, t)$, $F_{1_t}(z, t) \in C(D(z_0, t_0))$ sinflarga tegishli bo'lsin va $k_0 T^3 + 3q_0 T^2 < 6$ tengsizlik o'rinli bo'sin, u holda (11)-(13) masalaning $D(z_0, t_0)$ sohaga tegishli yagona klassik yechimi mavjud bo'ladi. Bunda $k_0 = \max_{t \in [0, t_0]} |k(t)|$, $q_0 = \max_{z \in [z_0 - t_0, z_0 + t_0]} |q(z)|$.

Isbot. (11)-(13) Koshi masalasini yechamiz. (11) tenglamani xarakteristikalari ustida integrallab, (12), (13) boshlang'ich shartlardan foydalanib quyidagi integral tenglamani hosil qilamiz:

$$v(z, t) = \frac{1}{2} [\eta(z - t) + \eta(z + t)] + \frac{1}{2} \int_{z-t}^{z+t} v(\xi) d\xi +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) v(\xi, \tau - \eta) d\eta - q(\xi) v(\xi, \tau) \right] d\xi d\tau \quad (16)$$

(16) integral tenglamaning ozod hadini quyidagi ko'rinishda belgilab olsak

$$v_0(z, t) = \frac{1}{2} [\eta(z - t) + \eta(z + t)] + \frac{1}{2} \int_{z-t}^{z+t} v(\xi) d\xi,$$

(16) integral tenglama

$$v(z, t) = v_0(z, t) + \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) v(\xi, \tau - \eta) d\eta - q(\xi) v(\xi, \tau) \right] d\xi d\tau \quad (17)$$

ko'rinishdagi tenglamaga keladi.

$v(z, t)$ funksiya teorema shartlariga ko'ra z va t o'zgaruvchilari bo'yicha ikki marta uzluksiz differensiallanuvchi bo'ladi. $v(z, t)$ funksiyani ikki marta t va ikki marta z o'zgaruvchilari bo'yicha differensiallab (11) tenglamaga qo'ysang, tenglamani ayniyatga keltirishini ko'rish mumkin. Boshlang'ich vaqt momentida, ya'ni $t = 0$ da (17) integral tenglama (12) shartni qanoatlantirishi, (17) integral tenglamani t o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha differensiallab, $t = 0$ boshlang'ich vaqt moment (13) shartni qanoatlantirishini ko'rish mumkin.

Shunday qilib, (11)-(13) Koshi masalasi (17) integral tenglamaga ekvivalent ekan. Shuning ushun (11)-(13) Koshi masalasi yechimini mavjudligini ko'rsatish o'rniga, unga ekvivalent bo'lgan (17) integral tenglama yechimini mavjudligini ko'rsatamiz. Buning uchun ketma-ket yaqinlashishlar (Pikar) usulidan foydalanamiz.

Quyidagi

$$v_0(z, t) = \frac{1}{2} [\eta(z - t) + \eta(z + t)] + \frac{1}{2} \int_{z-t}^{z+t} v(\xi) d\xi,$$

$$v_1(z, t) = v_0(z, t) + \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) v_0(\xi, \tau - \eta) d\eta - q(\xi) v_0(\xi, \tau) \right] d\xi d\tau,$$

$$v_2(z, t) = v_0(z, t) + \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) v_1(\xi, \tau - \eta) d\eta - q(\xi) v_1(\xi, \tau) \right] d\xi d\tau,$$

$$= \left| \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) v_{n-1}(\xi, \tau - \eta) d\eta - q(\xi) v_{n-1}(\xi, \tau) \right] d\xi d\tau \right| \leq$$

$$\leq \Phi_0 \left(\frac{k_0 T^3}{6} + \frac{q_0 T^2}{2} \right)^n,$$

... ..

bunda $\eta_0 = \max_{z \in [z_0 - t_0, z_0 + t_0]} |\eta(z)|$, $q_0 = \max_{z \in [z_0 - t_0, z_0 + t_0]} |v(z)|$.

Teorema shartiga ko'ra, $v_j(z, t)$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ funksiyalar $z_0 - t_0 \leq z \leq z_0 + t_0$ larda $D(z_0, t_0)$ sohadan chiqib ketmasligini ko'rsatadi. Shunday qilib, $z_0 - t_0 \leq z \leq z_0 + t_0$ tengsizlik bajarilsa, $v_j(z, t)$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ funksiyalar $D(z_0, t_0)$ sohada joylashar ekan.

Endi hadlari $v_j(z, t)$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ funksional ketma-ketliklardan tuzilgan funksional qatorning tekis yaqinlashuvchanligini ko'rsatamiz. Buning uchun

$$|v_1(z, t) - v_0(z, t)|, |v_2(z, t) - v_1(z, t)|, \dots, |v_n(z, t) - v_{n-1}(z, t)|, \dots$$

ayirmalarni baholaymiz:

$$|v_1(z, t) - v_0(z, t)| =$$

$$= \left| \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) v_0(\xi, \tau - \eta) d\eta - q(\xi) v_0(\xi, \tau) \right] d\xi d\tau \right| \leq$$

$$\leq \Phi_0 \left(\frac{k_0 T^2}{6} + \frac{q_0 T}{2} \right),$$

$$|v_2(z, t) - v_0(z, t)| = \left| \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) [v_1(\xi, \tau - \eta) - v_0(\xi, \tau - \eta)] d\eta - \right. \right.$$

$$\left. - q(\xi) [v_1(\xi, \tau - \eta) - v_0(\xi, \tau - \eta)] \right] d\xi d\tau \right| \leq \Phi_0 \left(\frac{k_0 T^3}{6} + \frac{q_0 T^2}{2} \right)^2,$$

... ..

$$\begin{aligned}
 |v_n(z, t) - v_{n-1}(z, t)| = & \\
 = & \left| \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) [v_{n-1}(\xi, \tau - \eta) - v_{n-2}(\xi, \tau - \eta)] d\eta - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - q(\xi) [v_{n-1}(\xi, \tau - \eta) - v_{n-2}(\xi, \tau - \eta)] \right] d\xi d\tau \right| \leq \Phi_0 \left(\frac{k_0 T^3}{6} + \frac{q_0 T^2}{2} \right)^n,
 \end{aligned}$$

Quyidagi funksional qatorni tuzib olamiz:

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} v_j(z, t).$$

Yuqoridagi olingan baholardan foydalanib, hosil bo'lgan funksional qatorni $(z, t) \in D(z, t)$ sohada sonli qator bilan quyidagicha mojarantlaymiz:

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} |v_j(z, t)| \leq \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \Phi_0 \left(\frac{k_0 T^3}{6} + \frac{q_0 T^2}{2} \right)^j$$

Sonli qator teorema shartida ko'rsatilgan $k_0 T^3 + 3q_0 T^2 < 6$ tengsizlikni qanoatlantiruvchi T larda yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi. Bundan Funksional qatorlarning tekis yaqinlashish haqidagi Veyershtrass teoremasiga ko'ra olingan funksional qator tekis yaqinlashuvchiligi kelib chiqadi. Bu natijadan (17) integral tenglama yordamida aniqlangan $v_j(z, t)$ funksiyalar ketma-ketligi $C^2(D(z, t))$ funksiyalar fazosida aniqlangan biror $v(z, t)$ funksiyaga tekis yaqinlashadi. Shunday qilib (11)-(13) Koshi masalasining $C^2(D(z, t))$ sinfga tegishli yechimi mavjudligini ko'rsatdik.

(17) integral tenglama yechimga ega ekanligini ko'rdik. Endi bu yechimning yagonaligini ko'rsatamiz. Buning uchun teskarisini faraz qilaylik, ya'ni (17) integral tenglama ikkita aynan teng bo'lmagan $v^1(z, t)$ va $v^2(z, t)$ yechimlarga ega bo'lsin:

$$v^1(z, t) = v_0(z, t) + \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) v^1(\xi, \tau - \eta) d\eta - q(\xi) v^1(\xi, \tau) \right] d\xi d\tau,$$

$$v^2(z, t) = v_0(z, t) + \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) v^2(\xi, \tau - \eta) d\eta - q(\xi) v^2(\xi, \tau) \right] d\xi d\tau.$$

$v^1(z, t)$ va $v^2(z, t)$ funksiyalar ayirmasini qarab, ularning farqini

$$w(z, t) = v^1(z, t) - v^2(z, t)$$

bilan belgilaymiz. Natijada

$$w(z, t) = \frac{1}{2} \iint_{D(z,t)} \left[\int_0^\tau K(\eta) w(\xi, \tau - \eta) d\eta - q(\xi) w(\xi, \tau) \right] d\xi d\tau. \quad (2.1.18)$$

bir jinsli ikkinchi tur Volterra integral tenglamasini olamiz. Har bir tayinlangan $t \in [0, T]$ da $z \in [z_0 - t_0, z_0 + t_0]$ bo'yicha $w(z, t)$ funksiyaning modul jihatdan supremumini $\tilde{w}(t)$ orqali belgilab, ya'ni:

$$\tilde{w}(t) = \sup_{z \in [z_0 - t_0, z_0 + t_0]} |w(z, t)|, \quad t \in [0, T].$$

U holda (2.1.18) integral tenglamadan

$$\tilde{w}(t) \leq \frac{k_0 + q_0}{2} \int_0^t \tilde{w}(\tau) d\tau, \quad t \in [0, T]$$

integral tengsizlik olinadi. Gronuolla — Bellman tengsizligiga ko'ra, oxirgi integral tengsizlik faqat $\tilde{w}(t) \equiv 0 \quad t \in [0, T]$ yechimga ega. Bundan esa \bar{D} sohada $w(z, t) \equiv 0$ yoki $v^1(z, t) = v^2(z, t)$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi. Shunday qilib (17) integral tenglama yagona yechimga ega ekan. **Teorema isbotlandi.**

MUHOKAMA

O'ylaymizki, ushbu ishda qo'llanilgan usullar ikkinchi tartibli integro-differensial tenglamalarini yechishda, yechimning mavjudligi va yagonaligini isbotlashda muhim muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bundan tashqari, matematik fizika tenglamalarida uchraydigan ayrim korrekt va nokorrekt qo'yilgan masalalarini yechishda ishdagi asosiy natijalardan foydalanilsa maqsadga muvoffiq bo'ladi.

XULOSA

Elektr xotiraga ega bo'lgan integro-differensial Maksvell tenglamasi uchun Koshi masalasi qo'yildi, masalaning yechimi mavjudligi va yagonaligi uchun asosiy teorema isbotlandi. Teoremani isbotlashda masala yechimining mavjudligi ketma-ket yaqinlashish (Pikar) usuli yordamida ko'rsatildi, Gronuolla — Bellman tengsizligiga asosan yagonaligi isbotlandi.

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